

EUPHRESCO

Modus operandi

March 2014

**Principles for a self-sustainable, long-term network
of phytosanitary (statutory plant health) research
funders and programmes managers**

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Introduction

The ERA-Net Project EUPHRESKO II is the continuance of EUPHRESKO, a policy-led coordination action, initiated by the EU Council Working Party of Chief Officers of Plant Health Services (COPHS). EUPHRESKO II started in January 2011 for three years, funded from the EU 7th framework programme. EUPHRESKO stands for **E**uropean **P**hytosanitary **R**esearch **C**ooperation and connects phytosanitary (statutory plant health) research funders (programme owners or managers) from 22 countries: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Portugal, Russia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and the UK.

The aim of the EUPHRESKO ERA Nets was to coordinate phytosanitary research at the European level. This involved coordination and co-operation between nationally-based phytosanitary research programmes in Europe for the first time through networking of research activities and a potential mutual opening or collaboration between national programmes. This coordination of national research has not been done significantly before EUPHRESKO nor has there been any significant trans-national funding of research, nor any alignment with EU-funded plant health research with nationally-funded research. EUPHRESKO therefore combines three main goals:

- Develop phytosanitary research policy and coordination at the EU-wide level.
- Optimise the research provision that underpins EU quarantine plant health policy development and implementation by reducing duplication and pooling resources.
- Increase the capacity of European phytosanitary science and research, in order to prevent the disappearance of expertise and maintain Europe's competitiveness in the global market. This supports EPPO's declaration of a *State of Emergency in Plant Health* in Madeira in 2004.

The projects were fully supported by the EU Council Working Party of Chief Officers for Plant Health Services (COPHS), The European Commission's Directorate General for Health and Consumer Protection (DG SANCO), the European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organisation (EPPO) and the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), all of which have European plant health responsibilities.

One component of the work plan of EUPHRESKO and EUPHRESKO II was the establishment of a self-sustainable, long-term cooperation network in Europe to ensure a durable coordination of European phytosanitary research. The initial basis for such a cooperation initiative has already been established through EUPHRESKO's activities since 2006.

Scope of the document

This Modus Operandi describes the organisation and the main functions of the long-term cooperation initiative EUPHRESKO. The network will represent the transformation of the EU financed EUPHRESKO ERA-Net into a self-sustainable network of interested partners, supported by EPPO for a two-year period. The document represents the proposed principles that will be necessary to initiate, operate and maintain a durable and self-sustainable network of phytosanitary research funders in Europe.

Definition of terms

Applied research	Original investigation undertaken in order to acquire new knowledge. It is, however, directed primarily towards a specific practical aim or objective support system
Basic/fundamental research	Experimental or theoretical work undertaken primarily to acquire new knowledge of the underlying foundation of phenomena and observable facts, without any particular application or use in view
Database	A collection of independent works, data or other materials which are arranged in a systematic or methodical way and are individually accessible by electronic or other means.
ERA-Net	European Research Area – Networking, element of the FP6 and FP7 specific programme aiming at integration and strengthening the European Research Area via coordination and mutual opening of national and regional research programmes
EUPHRESCO	EC sixth framework programme ERA-Net project entitled ‘European Phytosanitary (statutory plant health) Research Coordination’
EUPHRESCO II	EC seventh framework programme ERA-Net project, the continuation of EUPHRESCO with more partners and observers.
FP7	EU seventh framework programme for Research and Technological Development
Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)	Patent applications, patents, registered and unregistered design rights, copyrights, trade mark applications, trade marks, confidential information, trade secrets and any other similar proprietary rights for inventions, discoveries or technical information.
Pest	Any species, strain or biotype plant, animal or pathogenic agent injurious to plants or plant products [International Standard on Phytosanitary Measures No. 5, https://www.ippc.int/index.php?id=13399&tx_publication_pi1[showUid]=184195&frompage=13399&type=publication&subtype=&L=0#item] Here: including invasive non-native plants
Phytosanitary research	Research that deals with regulated quarantine pests, emerging pests with the potential to become quarantine pests (organisms new to countries, outbreaks in other countries, non-native invasive species relevant for or associated with, plants) and regulated non-quarantine pests (RNQP) in particular countries
Plant health	Regulated/statutory/quarantine plant health; all areas that come within the scope of the Community Plant Health Regime, e.g. pests (including pathogens and invasive weeds, GMO’s are excluded. An equivalent term is ‘phytosanitary’.

Regulated pest	A regulated quarantine pest or a regulated non-quarantine pest [ISPM No. 5]
Research	Includes basic and applied research and experimental development as defined by the OECD (OECD Frascati manual, 2002). Activities excluded from the definition of research are also defined by the Frascati manual (pages 30–46)
Transnational phytosanitary projects	Projects on phytosanitary (regulated plant health) topics involving participants (funders or researchers) from more than one country that are initiated and funded via the EUPHRESKO network.

Purpose and general provisions

- i. The purpose of this Modus Operandi is to specify the scope and principles under which a sustainable long-term network will operate, to organise the management of the network, to define rights and obligations of the parties and to define principles of the implementation of transnational projects.
- i. EUPHRESCO is a network of phytosanitary research funders or programme managers in Europe and the EPPO region. It may include eligible partners from other regions by invitation.
- ii. The network aims to enhance coordination and cooperation on phytosanitary research funding in the partner countries, thereby increasing the benefits from phytosanitary research for all partners. In particular, the outputs of this coordination and cooperation should contribute to:
 - Supporting European plant health policy development and its implementation
 - Supporting the maintenance and development of phytosanitary science capability
 - Optimising and making best use of national funds for plant health research whilst avoiding duplication
 - Increase communication and collaboration amongst partners and with other countries, relevant phytosanitary institutions and stakeholders on phytosanitary research.
- iii. The overarching aim is to help protect agriculture, horticulture, and forestry as well as plants in the environment in Europe and surrounding countries (e.g. the wider EPPO region), from regulated and emerging plant pests through effective trans-national research collaboration.
- iv. The Network will:
 - Identify and prioritise research needs for existing, new or emerging pests or issues of statutory concern that can be addressed through transnational research (Common Strategic Research Agenda)
 - Implement transnational research projects, disseminate research results and Network activities
 - Share information on national research projects and planning between Network Partners and other bodies as appropriate
 - Continue to advise the European Commission on plant health research priorities suitable for EU funding in the framework programmes, e.g. Horizon 2020
 - Maintain and enhance linkages with official plant health bodies in the world, key stakeholders and relevant networks or working groups

Network bodies, roles and responsibilities

Composition of the Network

- i. The Network will consist of Partners who represent phytosanitary research funders or programme managers in Europe, including other such bodies in third countries as appropriate in the European Plant Health context.
- ii. This refers mainly to ministries, governmental bodies or research institutions with their own research budgets but not to private organisations or enterprises.

Roles and Responsibilities

- i. Partners have to finance their own participation in the Network without entitlement to funding by any other party during the initial two-year period. Funding contributions from partners are expected thereafter in full, or in part if European-level co-financing is agreed.
- ii. Partners will have the right of representation on the Governing Board.
- iii. Partners will have full access to all information and might participate in all discussions on topics and topic descriptions.
- iv. Partners should actively contribute to the Network and its activities by participating in transnational research projects.
- v. Partners shall ensure contact with their own national stakeholders, e.g. via workshops, to provide contributions to the Common Strategic Research Agenda and the regular research initiation rounds

Governing Board of Network Partners

Composition of the Governing Board

- i. The Governing Board will be composed of duly authorised representatives of the ministry from each Network Partner or any other authorised person from the Partner organisation; representation may be given to another Partner (e.g. in the case of national agreements for one partner to represent several within the Governing Board, as per the EPPO Council model).
- ii. After having informed the others in writing, each Governing Board member shall have the right to replace its representative and/or to appoint a proxy.

- iii. Each representative shall name an alternative representative.

Decision Making in the Governing Board

- i. The Governing Board shall be chaired by a representative selected preferably by mutual agreement or by vote.
- ii. The Governing Board shall meet at the request of its chairperson or at any other time when necessary at the request of one of the Governing Board members. Meetings shall be convened by the chairperson with at least thirty (30) calendar days prior notice. This notice shall be accompanied by an agenda. The agenda shall be proposed by the chairperson. The agenda shall be deemed to be accepted unless one of the Governing Board members notifies the chairperson and the other Governing Board members in writing of additional points to the agenda, at the latest five (5) working days before the date of the meeting.
- iii. Minutes of the meetings of the Governing Board shall be transmitted to the Governing Board members within thirty (30) calendar days after the date of the meeting. The minutes shall be considered as accepted by the other Governing Board members if, within twenty (20) calendar days from receipt, no Governing Board member has objected in a traceable form to the chairperson.
- iv. Any decision requiring a vote at a Governing Board meeting must be identified as such on the pre-meeting agenda, unless there is unanimous agreement to vote on a decision at that meeting and all Governing Board members are present or represented.
- v. The Governing Board shall not deliberate and decide validly unless the majority of its members are present or represented (quorate). Where decisions are to be taken unanimously, all Governing Board members must be represented at the meeting.
- vi. However, any decision required to be taken by the Governing Board may be taken in meetings held via teleconference and subsequently confirmed in written form. In addition, Governing Board members may vote on a decision by email or by providing consent to a decision in writing via a signed undertaking, provided always that the number of votes is not less than the minimum number of votes that would be necessary to take such a decision at an actual meeting of the Governing Board and that the required number of votes are received to make the vote quorate and that consent has been requested from all Governing Board members.
- vii. Decisions shall be by consensus wherever possible, or if consensus cannot be reached, taken by the majority of the votes of the Governing Board present or represented by proxy at a quorate meeting, provided always that any member of the Governing Board who represents a Network Partner who will be concerned by the decision may veto such decisions.

viii. In voting each member of the Governing Board shall have one (1) vote.

Responsibilities of the Governing Board

The Governing Board shall be responsible for:

- Deciding whether or not to accept proposals made by the Network Management Group for launching of transnational research initiation rounds
- Deciding on publications referred to from the Network Management Group
- In the event of a dispute between Network Partners that cannot be settled amicably between the Parties concerned, the Governing Board can intervene in an attempt to resolve the dispute. A member of the Governing Board who is associated with any of the Parties in dispute shall not participate in its deliberations or vote on its decision, but can to the extent such decision affects their legitimate interests, veto such decision

Advisors

- i. The Network is expected to establish contact with organisations which influence plant health policy and with decision makers which should have input into the Network's activities, such organisations will be referred to as Advisors.
- ii. The circle of Advisors might be composed of:
 - Directorate General of Health and Consumers Protection (European Commission)
 - Directorate General of Research (European Commission)
 - Standing Committee of Plant Health (European Commission)
 - European Food Safety Authority (European Commission)
 - Chief Officers of Plant Health Services (EU Council Working Party)
 - EPPO Working Party on Phytosanitary Regulations
- i. This list can be extended by the Governing Board if appropriate.
- ii. Advisors might influence Network activities and might participate in Network meetings and can be included in all communication flows.
- iii. Advisors can be asked for advice and views on Network activities, such as identification transnational research projects and dissemination and knowledge exchange activities.
- iv. Advisors should be informed on important Network activities and decisions

Network Management Group

Composition and function of the Network Management Group

- i. The composition of the small Network Management Group (e.g. about 6 members) shall consist of the following members:
 - Selected Network partners and an elected Chair.
 - The EUPHRESCO Network Office (Co-ordination and secretariat functions)
- ii. The appointment of the Network Management Group will be carried out by the Governing Board.
- iii. Countries represented in EUPHRESCO with more than one partner should only be represented by one Network Management Group member
- iv. For a transition period, the members of the Network Management Group of the former ERA-Net EUPHRESCO II (about 9 members) will stay in duty until otherwise decided by the Governing Board.
- v. Any Network Management Group member may resign by delivering written notice to the Co-ordinator in consultation with their Governing Board Member. Such resignation shall be effective upon receipt unless it is specified to be effective at some other time or upon the happening of some other event.
- vi. The function of the NMG will be the on-going management of the Network and its activities, especially via the Network Office; it will report to the Governing Board.

Decision Making in the Network Management Group

- i. The Network Management Group shall be chaired by a member of the Network Management Group (selected by the Network Management Group preferably by mutual agreement or by voting and confirmed by the Governing Board) or by the Co-ordinator.
- ii. The Network Management Group shall meet about twice a year at the request of its chairperson or at any other time when necessary at the request of the majority of Network Management Group members. Meetings shall be convened by the chairperson and Network Office with at least thirty (30) calendar days prior notice. This notice shall be accompanied by an agenda. The agenda shall be proposed by the chairperson. The agenda shall be deemed to have been accepted unless one of the Network Management Group members notifies the chairperson and the other Network Management Group members in writing of additional points to the agenda, at the latest five (5) working days before the date of the meeting. Each Network Management Group member has to finance his own participation in a meeting.
- iii. Minutes of the meetings of the Network Management Group shall be transmitted by the chairperson (or their representative) to the Network Management Group members within

- thirty (30) calendar days after the date of the meeting. The minutes shall be considered as accepted if, within ten (10) calendar days from receiving, no Network Management Group member has objected in a traceable form to the chairperson. The exception shall be where a member has notified the chairperson in a traceable form of their absence during this period.
- iv. The agenda and the minutes of the meetings of the Network Management Group shall be transmitted by the chairperson (or the Network Office) to the Parties. The agenda shall be transmitted at the latest five (5) working days before the date of the meeting. The minutes shall be transmitted within forty (40) calendar days after the date of the meeting.
 - v. Any decision requiring a vote at a Network Management Group meeting must be identified as such on the pre-meeting agenda, unless there is unanimous agreement to vote on a decision at that meeting and all Network Management Group members are present or represented.
 - vi. The Network Management Group shall not deliberate and decide validly unless a majority of its members are present or represented (“quorate”).
 - vii. However, any decision required to be taken by the Network Management Group may be taken in meetings held via teleconference and subsequently confirmed in written form. In addition, Network Management Group members may vote on a decision by email or by providing consent to a decision in writing via a signed undertaking, provided always that the number of votes is not less than the minimum number of votes that would be necessary to take such a decision at an actual meeting of the Network Management Group and that the required number of votes are received to make the vote quorate and that consent has been requested from all Network Management Group members.
 - viii. Each Network Management Group member shall have one (1) vote.
 - ix. All decisions to be made by the Network Management Group shall be by consensus wherever possible, or if consensus cannot be reached, taken by the majority of the votes of the Network Management Group members present or represented by proxy at a quorate meeting, provided always that a Network Management Group member who represents a Party whose scope of work, time for performance, costs or liabilities are changed or whose information is to be published, disclosed or Disseminated or whose legitimate business interests may be affected or whose name is to be included in a press release, may veto such decisions.

EUPHRESCO Network Office

- i. The Network Office will be hosted by the European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organisation (EPPO) for a minimum period of two years.
- ii. The operation of the Network Office at EPPO (including the Co-ordination and secretariat functions) is financed by a fixed payment of EUPHRESCO Partners for a

- minimum period of two years.
- iii. Continuation after the fixed period has to be decided by the Governing Board before the end of the two-year period.
 - iv. The Network Office will handle administrative work, including:
 - Assisting the Network Management Group (NMG) and EUPHRESCO Partners to coordinate phytosanitary research and facilitate trans-national collaboration and research projects
 - Hosting and updating of the EUPHRESCO homepage to serve research coordination and knowledge exchange activities
 - Comprising the dissemination of important information, e.g. via newsletters, the EUPHRESCO homepage, through other EPPO activities (EPPO Workshops, Panels, etc) and EU-level fora (e.g. COPHS and SCPH)
 - Assisting in the organisation and facilitation of Network meetings and documentation (e.g. minutes, reporting) including reports for the EUPHRESCO Governing Board and its advisors, EPPO Council, COPHS, etc.
 - Assisting in updating of the Common Strategic Research Agenda and the maintenance of the EUPHRESCO databank on national phytosanitary research projects
 - v. The Network Office duties concerning the initiation and implementation of transnational projects include:
 - Preparation of research initiation
 - Surveillance of process steps operated via the online tool on the EUPHRESCO homepage, as
 - Identification of topics
 - Establishment of the list of topics
 - Topic coordinator assignment
 - Giving administrative support to the production of the short topic description (e.g. providing tools)
 - Giving support to the establishment of funding consortia
 - Giving support to the decision and agreement of funding mechanisms
 - Giving support to the production and signing of commitments
 - vi. The Network Office will be responsible for running the Network Secretariat functions, including:
 - External presentation of the Network on behalf of its Partners
 - Transmission of any documents and information connected with the Network between the parties concerned
 - Calling of meetings of parties concerned
 - Publication of network documents and wider knowledge exchange

- vii. The function of the EUPHRESCO Co-ordinator will be carried out within the Secretariat at the European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organisation (EPPO) for a minimum period of two years.
- viii. Continuation after the fixed period has to be decided by the Network Partners and the Governing Board before the end of the two-year period.
- ix. The Co-ordinator shall not be entitled to act or to make legally binding declarations on behalf of the network without agreement of the NMG and, if appropriate, the wider network partners.

Responsibilities of the Network Management Group and its EUPHRESCO Network Office (in EPPO)

- i. Reporting to the Governing Board, including making proposals to the Governing Board (e.g. for the launching of transnational research initiation rounds).
- ii. Individual NMG members may take the lead on specific areas (portfolios) of EUPHRESCO activity with support from the wider NMG and the Network Office.
- iii. Keeping direct contact with advisors (see page 10).
- iv. Initiating the maintenance and updating of the Common Strategic Research Agenda that will reflect national research agendas of the Network Partners. It will constitute the actual status quo on phytosanitary research needs and gaps.
- v. Initiating the maintenance and updating of the database on national phytosanitary research projects, which give an overview on national phytosanitary projects in the partner countries including the annual budget.
- vi. Advising the European Commission on plant health priorities in their framework programs according to the mandate given to EUPHRESCO by the Chief Officers of Plant Health Services (COPHS) in June 2007 (which may require re-mandating).
- vii. Initiating periodic independent evaluation of the Network and its activities with approval of the Governing Board.
- viii. Establishing linkages to other networks, ERA-NETs and ERA-Net platforms or other relevant national, regional or international plant health organisations. These contacts are not restricted to plant health but might comprise a broad range of relevant disciplines and research sectors. In addition the consortium should seek regular contact with organisations who are not yet members of EUPHRESCO.
- ix. Initiation of the further development of the Network's homepage and wider knowledge exchange activities. The website shall offer possibilities for publication of research results from transnational projects and information on all network activities including

identified topics and topic descriptions.

- x. This list is not exclusive and might be modified with different or additional activities as needed.

Research Co-operation

- i. The initiation, planning, funding and realisation of trans-national research projects will be the main task of the EUPHRESCO Network and will be mainly assisted and facilitated by the Network Office.
- ii. The process starts with the identification of relevant topics for transnational phytosanitary research in compliance with the EUPHRESCO scope (page 7).
- iii. Topics should correspond with the topic selection criteria noted in the EUPHRESCO tool book.
- iv. Funders of at least two different countries have to participate in a topic that will be accomplished under the EUPHRESCO Network.
- v. Topic identification might start any time, as needed, but should aim to be done at least once a year as part of a regular routine. Periods and frequency of topic identification processes should comply with needs in the plant health sector and accord to the situation with the possibility to react in quickly on emerging problems.
- vi. Topics can be proposed by any Network Partner, Governing Board member or an Advisor principally via the member's area of the Network Homepage or other agreed means.
- vii. Interested funders have to decide on a topic coordinator, who will be responsible for the initiation of the development of an appropriate topic description. The topic description should identify the problem and the outcomes required, but not the methods or approaches. The finalised topic description will be published on the Network internal Homepage to enable funders to decide on a participation in the topic.
- viii. The following implementation process of transnational projects will be open to all interested parties. Interested funders are requested to get in contact with the topic coordinator to form a funders' consortium. The number of funders involved will not be limited. Interested funders do not have to be Network Partners.
- ix. The funding mechanism, e.g. real common pot, virtual common pot or non-competitive mechanism (or a mixed mechanism) and the project budget will be

determined by the funders involved.

- x. The implementation of the individual trans-national projects will not be steered by the Network. It will be solely the responsibility of interested funders (funding consortium).
- xi. The toolbox and all necessary information and documents for the initiation and implementation of transnational projects that had been developed in the ERA-Net EUPHRESCO will stay available on the Network Homepage.
- xii. Results from transnational projects initiated by the EUPHRESCO Network should be made accessible to all Network Partners as soon as possible.
- xiii. Network Partners might commit themselves not to publish any results before a given period of time, to enable the research consortium to produce an official publication.

IPR & Publications

Intellectual Property Rights

Ownership of IP

Each Party shall retain ownership of its own Pre-Existing Know-How developed prior to entering into a transnational project.

Knowledge shall be the property of the Party performing the work leading to the development of that Knowledge.

Joint Ownership

If, in the course of carrying out work on a transnational project, a joint invention, design or work is made (and more than one Party is contributor to it), and if the features of such joint invention design or work are such that it is not possible to separate them for the purpose of applying for, obtaining and/or maintaining the relevant patent protection or any other intellectual property right, the Parties concerned agree that they may jointly apply to obtain and/or maintain the relevant right. The Parties concerned shall seek to agree between themselves arrangements for applying for, obtaining and maintaining such rights on a case-by-case basis.

Where there are several co-owners, the Parties concerned may for administrative purposes assign ownership to a single Party. This could be affected by a joint ownership agreement between all of the Parties. Such an agreement must set out how issues such as decision making in relation to the Knowledge and sharing of costs and revenue from exploitation of the Knowledge are to be dealt with.

Publications

Publications

- i. In publications proper references to the all participating parties and to the EUPHRESKO Network shall be made.
- ii. For the avoidance of doubt it is stated that unless otherwise agreed between the parties concerned no party shall have the right to publish or allow the publication of data which includes knowledge of another party, pre-existing know-how of another party or confidential information of another party even where such data is amalgamated with such first party's knowledge, pre-existing know-how or other information, document or material.
- iii. All authors are required to indicate their membership of EUPHRESKO in all publications and communications relating to transnational projects initiated under EUPHRESKO.

Annex I - EUPHRESCO and EPPO Relationships and Governance Lines

